

SCHOOL HEADS' COLLABORATIVE LEADERSHIP, TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE AND PUPILS' ACADEMIC OUTCOMES

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School Heads' Collaborative Leadership, Teachers' Performance and Pupils' Academic Outcomes

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the influence of collaborative leadership practices of the school heads to teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic achievements. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized and the Statistical tools used in the study were mean, standard deviation, frequency count, and percentages to analyze the extent of the collaborative leadership practices in terms of shared school governance, collaborative decision-making, and stakeholders' participation; teachers' teaching performance; and pupils' academic achievement. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of teachers' teaching performance and the extent of collaborative leadership of school heads and the significant relationship between teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic achievement. Findings revealed that collaborative leadership in terms of shared school governance, collaborative decision-making, and stakeholders' participation were practiced to the "Very High Extent" while majority of the teachers that is 60% had a "Very Satisfactory" teaching performance and majority of the pupils that is 57% had a "Very Satisfactory" academic achievements. Subsequently, it was also found out in the Statistical Treatment of data that collaborative leadership of school heads in terms of shared school governance, collaborative decision-making, and stakeholders' participation were "Significantly Correlated" or had "Significant Relationship" to teachers' teaching performance while teachers' teaching performance had "Significant Correlation" to pupils' academic achievements. As a summary, it was recommended that school heads must continue to practice the collaborative leadership to stimulate teachers improve teachers' teaching effectiveness and pupils to develop their academic achievements.

Keywords: *collaborative leadership, shared school governance, collaborative decision-making, stakeholders' participation, and pupils' academic achievement*

Introduction

Collaborative leadership style of school heads in the public schools is extensively considered as crucial mediating factor to foster teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic outcomes as well as institutional innovations, advancements, and capacity building in teaching and learning practices. School heads' collaborative leadership style is indissolubly associated to day-to-day schools' operations as the strategic driver to educational change and success.

The framework of the study is bounded on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to RA 9155 which defined the role of the school heads in instructional leadership and administrative performance to form a team with teachers and learning facilitators for delivery of quality educational programs, projects, and services and DM 50, s. 2020 on the professional development priorities for school heads which shall support the realization of DepEd's goal of continuous upskilling and reskilling of teachers and school leaders that will result in better learning outcomes.

The Department of Education is presently active in implementing the fundamental reforms that includes efforts for human resource development at all levels to support quality performance of schools and learners. The Department's package of policy reforms known as the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) seeks "to systematically improve critical regulatory, institutional, structural, financial, cultural, physical and informational conditions affecting basic education provision, access and delivery on the ground. These policy reforms are expected to create critical changes necessary to further accelerate, broaden, deepen and sustain the improved education effort already being started" (BESRA PIP, 2006).

Tan and Wu (2020) asserted that collaborative leadership of school heads which are consistently aligned with the school missions and visions with actions is the cornerstone to establish productive schools. Hence, it is acquiescent to nurture schools with school heads' collaborative leadership in order to achieve the educational goals and improved institutional performance.

Additionally, school heads' leadership and teachers' performance constitute the primary sources of effective and collaborative leadership in school that are instrumental in improving pupils' school performance and academic outcomes (Parveen, et al, 2021). School leadership exerts a measurable, albeit indirect, effect on pupils' learning. It helps achieve educational goals through strategic actions that focus on academic processes.

Moreover, Marzano (2021) avowed that school heads directly and indirectly influenced teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic outcomes. Collaborative leaders stimulate teachers to improve teaching performance for pupils' academic and intellectual development. It was also emphasized that teachers' personal commitment to uphold quality instruction matter most to pupils' academic outcomes.

In a similar investigation, Parveen, et al (2022) found that school heads' leadership is accountable for facilitating school effectiveness

which help in improving modern knowledge and classroom instruction that likely optimize educational achievements and enhance teacher job performance and pupils' academic outcomes.

Saleem et al (2020) revealed that teachers' teaching performance has always been empirically proved to be related to school heads' behaviors and to their collaborative leadership styles. Further, it was found that school heads' collaborative leadership style and teachers' teaching performance are considerably intertwined with each other.

Subsequently, school heads' collaborative leadership practices include facilitating collaborative strategic planning that involves all stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and administrative and support staff aside from regular instructional supervision of classes in order to provide feedback on instructional practices of teachers and its impact on pupils.

Consequently, teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic outcomes are mediated with the school heads' collaborative leadership skills as they are stimulated to inspire teachers to improve performance, show creativity and innovativeness in teaching in order to help improve pupils' learning and academic outcomes.

However, Saleem, et al (2020) reported that school heads' leadership has no direct influence to pupils' academic outcomes because it is the main responsibility of teachers to help improve pupils' academic achievements and learning performance.

It is based on the above-stated considerations that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to ascertain the mediating effect of school heads' collaborative leadership style to teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic outcomes

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the influence of school heads' collaborative leadership practices in the relationship between teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic outcomes. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of school heads' collaborative leadership practices in terms of the following;
 - 1.1. shared school governance;
 - 1.2. collaborative decision-making;
 - 1.3. stakeholders' participation?
2. What is the teachers' level of teaching performance?
3. What is the pupils' academic outcomes when they are categorized as;
 - 3.1. outstanding;
 - 3.2. very satisfactory;
 - 3.3. satisfactory;
 - 3.4. fairly satisfactory;
 - 3.5. did not meet expectation?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the school heads' collaborative leadership practices and teachers' teaching performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic achievements?

Methodology

Research Design

The study will utilize the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations. In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population. Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of survey questionnaires, interview, and focused-group discussion (FGD).

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the teachers of Lumbia Central School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro. There were seventy-five (75) teacher-respondents of the study who answered the survey questionnaire on school heads' collaborative leadership practices and their teaching performance based on the individual performance and commitment review forms. The respondents were purposively chosen for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The study was adapted from the research of Marzano (2021) who asserted that school heads' collaborative leadership performance

stimulate teachers to improve teaching performance and influence pupils' academic outcomes. The survey instrument is composed of three (3) major components. The first component is on the school heads' collaborative leadership practices in terms of shared school governance, collaborative decision-making, and stakeholders' participation. Each of the items is composed of ten (10) indicators.

Additionally, the second component of the survey questionnaire is the teachers' teaching performance based on the individual performance commitment review of teachers in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, community linkages and professional engagements, performance of various teaching-related works. Part 3 is on the pupils' academic outcomes which are categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro. The same permission was asked by the researcher to the teacher-respondents to participate in the study and to the parents of pupils-respondents to allow the researcher utilize their child's academic outcomes as the variable of this study. Moreover, the parents were assured that the data gathered was treated to its highest confidentiality and used for research purposes only. After the respondents provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment were utilized to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the school heads' collaborative leadership practices in terms of shared school governance, collaborative decision making, and stakeholders' participation.

For Problem 2, frequency and percentages were used to present the teachers' teaching performance.

For Problem 3, frequency and percentages was used to present the pupils' academic outcomes.

For Problem 4, Pearson-r was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the teachers' teaching performance and pupils' academic outcomes.

For Problem 5, Pearson-r was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the school heads' collaborative leadership practices and teachers' teaching performance.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on ol heads' collaborative leadership and its influence on the relationship between teaching performance and pupils' academic outcomes. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the problem presented.

Problem 1. What is the Extent of School Heads' Collaborative Leadership Practices in terms of the following: Shared School Governance, Collaborative Decision-making and, Stakeholders' Participation?

Collaborative leadership practices among school heads in the public schools is expansively reflected as critical interceding aspect in fostering teachers' teaching effectiveness and pupils' academic outcomes. This will also inspire institutional innovations and developments, capacity building in teaching and learning practices, and transformation of the processes for global competitiveness.

Table 1.1 shows the mean distribution of the extent of school heads' collaborative leadership practices in terms of shared school governance.

Table 1.1. Mean Distribution of School Heads' Collaborative Leadership Practices in terms of Shared School Governance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Communicates to stakeholders of programs towards the achievement of goals and objectives of the school.	4.56	.641	Very High Extent
2. Maintains transparency of records and expenses of the school.	4.66	.577	Very High Extent
3. Enforces rules and regulations in allowable and authorized school contribution	4.69	.568	Very High Extent
4. Performs instructional supervision (checks weekly work plan, monitor teacher's attendance, observes classes and distribution learning materials)	4.69	.544	Very High Extent
5. Undertakes inspection of school campus and equipment and facilities	4.65	.557	Very High Extent
6. Establishes rapport with parents and students	4.68	.549	Very High Extent
7. Establishes open & two-way communication with teachers	4.68	.549	Very High Extent
8. Encourages and motivates teachers to develop positivity in work amidst challenges	4.68	.549	Very High Extent
9. Emphasizes collaboration and empowerment	4.68	.549	Very High Extent
10. Encourages teachers for professional growth and development	4.68	.549	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.67	.563	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of school heads' collaborative leadership practices in terms of shared school governance. Overall, the respondents rated the shared school governance as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.67 (SD=.563). This result indicates that the collaborative leadership practices in terms of shared school governance was extremely utilized by the school heads. It can be deduced based on findings that school heads involved teachers, parents, and stakeholders in every school programs and projects for the attainment of school's goals and objectives. It can be deduced based on findings that it is imperative for the school heads to maintain the practice of shared school governance in order to promote participation and collaboration among internal and external stakeholders.

As emphasized by Tan and Wu (2020) that collaborative leadership of school heads helps achieve the school's missions and visions and a cornerstone to establish more productive schools. It is instrumental in achieving the educational goals and objectives and facilitates institutional performance.

The indicators "Enforces rules and regulates in allowable and authorized school contribution" and "Performs instructional supervision such as checking weekly work plan, monitor teachers' attendance, observes classes and distribution of learning materials" obtained the highest mean value of 4.69 (SD=.568) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that in collaborative leadership practices in terms of shared school governance such as imposing mandated and authorized school contributions and the performance of school heads' administrative functions were extremely implemented and practiced.

This finding was supported by Marzano (2021) who pointed out that school heads performed exceptionally their administrative functions in order to exemplify leadership and attain specific school's goals and objectives as mandated and inherent in their administrative and instructional responsibilities.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.56 (SD= .641) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "Communicates to stakeholders of programs towards the achievement of goals and objectives of the school". The result indicates that school head's function of maintaining communication between and among stakeholders on the programs planned and implemented in school was extremely and enormously practiced. It is imperative for the school heads to properly communicate to the stakeholders the activities and development programs of the school in order to stimulate collaboration and participation.

Parveen, et al (2021) averred that school's stakeholders need to be informed through proper communication channel on the development programs and projects of the school to sustain collaboration and partnership. Additionally, it was added that school heads need to forge collaboration and partnership through constant open communication and updating of the school's development and projects implemented.

Table 1.2. Mean Distribution of School Heads' Collaborative Leadership Practices in terms of Collaborative Decision-Making

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Empowers teachers to state the clear vision of the school	4.58	.547	Very High Extent
2. Empowers teachers to establish safe learning environment	4.55	.552	Very High Extent
3. Allows teachers to help monitors school performance	4.45	.552	Very High Extent
4. Allows teachers to coordinates curriculum implementation	4.40	.545	Very High Extent
5. Invites and encourages different or divergent points of view	4.38	.612	Very High Extent
6. Asks teachers on the needs for human and material resources	4.29	.652	Very High Extent
7. Selects and sends teachers in professional development	4.25	.659	Very High Extent
8. Collaborate with teachers on shared ownership of goal setting and decision-making	4.25	.659	Very High Extent
9. Collaborate with teachers in creating a productive culture	4.25	.659	Very High Extent
10. Collaborate with teachers to create a peaceful learning atmosphere.	4.25	.659	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.37	.610	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.2 displays the mean distribution of school heads' collaborative leadership practices in terms of collaborative decision-making. Overall, the respondents rated the collaborative decision-making as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.37 (SD=.610). This result indicates that the collaborative decision-making was extremely practiced by the school heads. It can be deduced based on findings that school heads continuously encouraged teachers to participate in planning and decision-making in school's related activities. It is imperative for the school head to empower teachers and include them in making decisions to resolve problems related to school and students' issues.

As pointed out by Bas and Bas (2020), collaborative decision making is an agent for developmental change in school organization because teachers are given the opportunity to take part in sharing their ideas and brainstorm to make relevant suggestions to address the challenges at hand.

Further, it was emphasized that collaborative decision-making impacts teachers' performance because they develop the feelings of ownership of the school organization and will conceptualize organizational variables such as teachers' motivation, school structure, school culture as mediating the effects of leadership on school outcomes continue to share a common assumption.

The indicator "Empower teachers to state the clear vision of the school" obtained the highest mean value of 4.58 (SD=.547) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that in collaborative leadership practices in terms of collaborative decision-

making allows or empowers teachers to participate in the crafting the clear strategies to achieve the school's vision. It is imperative that school heads will empower teachers to help state the clear vision of the school in order to stimulate collaboration, participation, and involvement.

This finding was supported by Marzano (2021) who pointed out that school heads ability to collaborate and involve teachers in the stating clear objectives to achieve the school's vision and mission is an exceptional administrative functions of the school administrators in order to attain the mandated and inherent administrative functions.

Salas and Gronn (2020) emphasized that school heads' practice of leadership involves developing a collective vision for transformation and then empowering teachers to work collaboratively to achieve the schools' vision. Collaborative leadership tends distribute and share equal responsibilities and roles among teachers in school and therefore achievements of school goals and vision is not measured by the performance of the school heads alone.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.25 (SD= .659) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicators "Selects and sends teachers to professional development"; "Collaborate with teachers on shared ownership of goal setting and decision-making"; "Collaborate with teachers in creating a productive culture"; and, "Collaborate with teachers to create a peaceful learning atmosphere". It can be deduced based on findings that school heads enormously provide opportunities to teachers for professional development by giving equal chance to attend seminars, trainings, and conferences. Empower teachers through collaboration in goal-setting and decision-making and above all stimulating teachers to create a peaceful and conducive learning atmosphere in school.

These findings were supported by Parveen, et al (2021) who suggested that school heads shall not only forge collaboration and partnership among teachers for the successful implementation of the school's projects and programs but they also provide opportunities for teachers' professional development, collaborate in goal-setting and decision-making as well as in creating a school environment supportive to the psycho-social and emotional needs of learners.

Further, Villa (2020) stated that collaborative or participative leaders stress the decision making processes of the group. Collaborative leadership rests on the grounds that will enhance organizational effectiveness and rests its case for participation on democratic principles.

Table 1.3. Mean Distribution of School Heads' Collaborative Leadership Practices in terms of Stakeholders' Participation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Fosters shared commitment among stakeholders to support school programs and activities	4.37	.610	Very High Extent
2. Forges collaboration and participation among stakeholders on school's program and activities	4.30	.593	Very High Extent
3. Forges stakeholders support and collaboration in school governance	4.33	.650	Very High Extent
4. Involves the stakeholders in shared vision and enabling change and development	4.38	.540	Very High Extent
5. Involves stakeholders in school improvement plan and development framework	4.34	.581	Very High Extent
6. Involves stakeholders in crafting policies in improving pupils' school attendance and participation	4.31	.598	Very High Extent
7. Encourages stakeholders to directly involve in creating an effective learning environment.	4.34	.608	Very High Extent
8. Involves stakeholders in planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of school development plan	4.30	.636	Very High Extent
9. Engages stakeholders in dialogue that builds understanding of goals and strategies behind the project.	4.25	.649	Very High Extent
10. Encourages stakeholders to engage in identifying social, environmental, and educational issues that must be addressed immediately.	4.26	.703	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.32	.617	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1.3 displays the mean distribution of school heads' collaborative leadership practices in terms of stakeholders' participation. Overall, the respondents rated the stakeholders' participation as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.32 (SD=.617). This result indicates that stakeholders' collaboration was extremely practiced by the school heads. It can be deduced based on findings that school heads continuously encourage, involve, and stimulate stakeholders to participate and collaborate in school activities, programs, and projects.

Gupta and Verma (2020) stated that stakeholders' participation plays the critical role in the successful implementation of school's projects and programs. School heads' administrative functions involve stimulating stakeholders to collaborate in school improvement plan and school's development framework. They are also involved in crafting policies in improving pupils' school attendance and participation.

The indicator "Involves the stakeholders in shared vision and enabling change and development" obtained the highest mean value of 4.38 (SD=.540) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that in collaborative leadership practices in terms of stakeholders' participation was extremely practiced and implemented. It is imperative for the school head to empower the school's

stakeholders to collaborate and participate in school activities and programs.

This finding was supported by Cheng and Tsui (2020) averred that school head's administrative function includes forging collaboration with stakeholders in shared vision and to enable them to participate in school's development projects and programs.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.25 (SD= .649) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "Engages stakeholders in dialogue that builds understanding of goals and strategic behind the project". It can be deduced based on findings that school heads immensely involve stakeholders in charting the goals of the school organization and engaged in the implementation of the school programs and projects.

Parveen, et al (2021) suggested that school heads shall not only forge collaboration and partnership among teachers but also engage stakeholders in planning and building understanding of goals and strategies for the successful implementation of the school's projects and programs but they also provide opportunities for teachers' professional development, collaborate in goal-setting and decision-making as well as in creating a school environment supportive to the psycho-social and emotional needs of learners.

Problem 2. What is the level of teacher's teaching performance when they are categorized as; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and Poor?

Table 2 presents the level of teachers' teaching performance categorized as Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and poor.

Table 2. *Frequency Distribution of Teachers' Teaching Performance*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	25	33%
Very Satisfactory	45	60%
Satisfactory	5	7%
Unsatisfactory	0	0
Poor	0	0
Total	75	100%

It can be asserted that out of 75 respondents, 45 (60%) had a "Very Satisfactory" teaching performance while only 5 or 7% of the respondents had a "Satisfactory" teaching performance. This indicates that majority of the teachers performed extremely and reasonably high due to the school head's ability to empower teachers through collaboration and participation in school-related activities.

It can also be asserted that the higher percentage of teachers' teaching performance was inspired by the school head's collaborative leadership practices which stimulate teachers to perform better in their teaching and non-teaching assignments.

This finding was supported by Murphy and Hallinger (2020) who exemplified that collaborative leadership, authority, and influence are factors that hypothetically influence teachers' teaching performance effectiveness and pupils' learning outcomes and school performance. The school heads' choice of democratic, participative, and collegial leadership styles positively affects and stimulate teachers' performance.

Additionally, collaborative leadership practices inspire teachers to develop resiliency in facing increasingly difficult or complex school and classroom situations with varied characteristics, behaviors, and diversity of learners' learning needs. Resiliency in facing uncertainties, ambiguity, and high expectations for innovation and reform in education. Further, it was highlighted that school heads necessitate to embrace more challenging tasks of forging collaboration with teachers, parents, learners, and other stakeholders in the process (Deal and Peterson, 2021).

Problem 3. What is the level of Pupils' Academic Achievements when they are categorized as; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectations?

Table 3. *Frequency Distribution of Pupils' Academic Achievements*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	21	28%
Very Satisfactory	43	57%
Satisfactory	8	11%
Fairly Satisfactory	3	4%
Did not meet expectations	0	0
Total	75	100%

It can be gleaned on the table that out of 75 students, 43 (57%) achieved a "Very Satisfactory" academic performance while only 3 or 4% achieved a "Fairly Satisfactory" academic achievements. This means that majority of the pupils were able to performed extremely high because of the well-motivated and empowered teachers. They are teachers who can stimulate, encourage, and inspire pupils to

perform better in their school and academic activities.

Thus, it is imperative that teachers should always inspire, encourage, and stimulate greater academic achievements in school. Fullan (2020) suggests that school leadership facilitates conditions that support effective teaching and learning as well as build capacity for professional learning and change. Further, leadership that intensifies the schools' capacity for improving teachers' instructional expertise will positively influence pupils' learning outcomes. School heads' leadership practices represents a key target of strategic leadership efforts designed to affect teacher practice and students' academic achievements.

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of teachers' teaching performance and the extent of school head's collaborative leadership practices in terms of; Shared School Governance, Collaborative Decision-Making, and Stakeholders' Participation?

Table 4. *Statistical Result of the Interplay Between the Collaborative Leadership Practices and Teachers' Teaching Performance*

School Head's Collaborative Leadership Practices	Teachers' Teaching Performance			
	(r)	Sig	Interpretation	H01
Shared School Governance	.572	.000	Signifies Moderate Correlation	Rejected
Collaborative Decision-Making	.789	.000	Means High Relationship	Rejected
Stakeholders' Participation	.735	.000	Means High Relationship	Rejected

Table 4 presents the interplay between the collaborative Leadership Practices of the School Head and Teachers' Teaching Performance. The table depicts that collaborative Leadership in terms of shared school governance signifies moderate correlation to teachers' teaching performance as evident by the computed r value of .572 which is higher than the significant value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. It can be argued logically, that school head's collaborative leadership practice in terms of shared school governance was significantly correlated to teachers' teaching performance.

As Anderson and Wahlstrom (2021) pointed out, collaborative leadership practices in terms of shared school governance influence teachers' teaching performance because it helps stimulates, encourages, and inspires teachers to perform better in their teaching performance.

Further, it was emphasized that teaching effectiveness depends on the emotional, cognitive, and behavioral competence of a teacher. Additionally, teacher with such qualities is termed as effective teacher because there is a link between the school and the learners. They are considered effective teachers because they can use their teaching skills to bring out the best in a pupil thus increasing the school's effectiveness. Furthermore, measuring the teaching effectiveness of a teacher is also very necessary as it helps in improving the quality of teaching. The periodic feedback also helps in recognizing the gaps in teaching and in preparation of corrective strategies.

Additionally, collaborative leadership of school head in terms of collaborative decision-making has higher relationship with teachers' teaching performance as evident the computed r value of .789 which is higher than the significant value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. It can be argued logically, that school head's collaborative leadership practice in terms of collaborative decision-making was significantly related to teachers' teaching performance.

Subsequently, stakeholders' participation has high relationship to teachers' teaching performance as shown in r value of .735 which is higher than the significant value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. It can be argued rationally, that school head's collaborative leadership practice in terms of stakeholders' participation influences teachers' teaching performance.

These findings were supported by Fullan (2020) who averred that school heads' collaborative leadership in the areas of collaboration and decision-making and stakeholders' participation predict school effectiveness and productivity increase, communication is improved, mutual trust, active empathy, access to help, lenience in judgment, and courage are all elements of collaborative organizations through the school heads.

Consequently, school heads' collaborative leadership effects on teachers' teaching performance are indirect, this perspective still requires an uncomfortable assumption about the role of leadership in complex organizations. Leadership influences change and school improvement.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between Pupils' Academic Achievements and Teachers' Teaching Performance?

Table 5. *Statistical Result of the Interplay Between Pupils' Academic Achievements and Teachers' Teaching Performance*

Teaching Performance	Pupils' Academic Achievements			
	(r)	Sig	Interpretation	H01
Teachers' Teaching Performance	.701	.000	Means High Relationship	Rejected

Table 5.1 presents the interplay between the pupils' academic achievements and teachers' teaching performance. The table depicts that teachers' teaching performance has high relationship to pupils' academic achievement as evident by the computed r value of .701 which is higher than the significant value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued understandably, that pupils'

academic achievement was influenced by teachers' teaching performance.

Velasquez (2020) avowed that pupils' academic achievements were improved through teachers' teaching effectiveness and the cooperative learning approach utilized by the effective and efficient teachers. Additionally, the influenced of teachers' teaching effectiveness through the use of different learning strategies such as cooperative learning approach has motivated pupils to achieve the desired academic and learning performance. Further, it was also emphasized that teachers' teaching effectiveness does not only help improved pupils' academic achievement but also it promotes pupils' social interdependence and cohesion which motivate them to perform better in their school and academic activities.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The Collaborative leadership practices of school heads in terms of shared school governance, collaborative decision-making, and stakeholders' participation in school activities and programs promote, inspire, stimulate, and motivate participation among teachers, students, and stakeholders in every school activity, programs, and projects which generally help achieve or attain the school's goals, objectives, mission and vision.

Teachers' teaching performance is the results of teachers' personal commitment and dedication to the teaching profession coupled with their professional preparation through trainings, seminar workshops, master class, graduate and post graduate studies will contribute teachers' teaching effectiveness. Additionally, the school environment and culture created by the school heads and teachers; the technical support provided by the school heads and master teachers as well as the collaborative leadership practices of the school heads are factors considered to influence teachers' teaching performance and effectiveness.

Pupils' academic achievements are influenced by pupils' mental and cognitive development and maturity, willingness and internal motivation to learn and teachers' teaching effectiveness as well as parental support. Additionally, pupils' academic achievements can be attributed to pupils' time management, self-motivation, engagement, behavior, and attitudes are the ke factors governing their academic success.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will encourage school heads to utilize collaborative leadership practices to inspire more teachers to improve teaching performance. Additionally, school heads should always be inspired to forge collaboration and partnership with their teachers and stakeholders in order to successfully implement school's projects and programs.

School Principals/School Heads will continue to practice and utilize the collaborative leadership practices and inspire teachers to collaborate with the stakeholders to implement the school's program and project in order to achieve school's goals and objectives.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to develop strategies to improve their teaching effectiveness through a collaborative learning approaches and learner-centered strategic intervention materials responsive to the pupils' learning deficiencies.

Parents will be able to provide support in the collaborative learning activities designed by teachers to improve their pupils' academic achievements. Parental support is indispensable in the academic success of their children, thus, the need to always encourage them to participate and collaborate with teachers in providing necessary learning support.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders will be able to provide more support to school activities especially in the implementation of the school's program and projects.

Future Researchers will be encouraged to conduct a similar study on the efficiency and effectiveness of the collaborative leadership practices of the school heads to stimulate teachers and stakeholders' participation in the implementation of schools' projects and programs.

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